

D6.2 Report on the project's communication and dissemination activities - Years 1 and 2

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Executive summary

This deliverable summarises the communication and dissemination activities of the ECS project during the first two years of its work plan (August 1, 2022 - July 31, 2024). **Chapter 1. The Communication and Dissemination Plan** in a nutshell offers a summary of the **Communication and Dissemination plan** (WP6.1) submitted on November 30, 2022, to provide the context in which the activities were developed.

Chapter 2. Main activities and results presents the concrete actions carried out: the development of social media starting from the existing channels of the EU-Citizen.Science project, the production of videos and the digital magazine. Finally, ECS's presence at international events was massive and involved all partners, both beneficiaries and affiliated entities. Our involvement in the HRB program has also laid the groundwork for further increased visibility. International collaboration in Europe and globally has been cultivated through multiple channels that will become more strategic in the next two years (**Chapter 3. Global collaborations**).

Chapter 4 Conclusions and next steps highlights the collective effort that has made it possible to achieve excellent results, as also quantitatively

testified by the KPIs, which have been largely achieved and exceeded.

Here a summary of the **main results**:

- The development of a strategic communication and dissemination plan with the collaboration of partners
- The creation of a recognizable visual and brand identity
- The development of social media channels and the growth of engagement and community of more than 12.000 followers
- The production of a digital magazine in collaboration with the ECS collaboration group, that reach out to more than 1500 readers
- The production of two videos
- The organisation and participation in dozens of national and international events
- Strengthening ties with national and international networks and associations including the Citizen Science Global Partnership.

1. The Communication and Dissemination Plan in a nutshell

We present here a summary of the **D6.1 Communication and Dissemination** plan delivered by ECSA on November 30th 2022, which is our guideline and inspiration for all activities of communication and dissemination. While the original plan was labelled as “sensitive”, and as such it is not publicly available, this report is public and interested readers might find this summary useful to better understand the context and the frame within which the communication and dissemination activities are developed.

The metaphor and the visual identity

The European Citizen Science project has the overall objective to widen and strengthen the citizen science community in Europe. It is committed to push modern science towards open science, will contribute to make Europe positioned as a leader in citizen science throughout the entire research and innovation system through capacity building and awareness, the creation of a European Citizen Science Academy and the establishment of a network of citizen science ambassadors.

We decided to visualise such a complex structure as an archipelago within a vast ocean, the latter representing the realm of citizen science. The islands, referring to the organisations, academy, media, communities, news and events and resources, belong to the same system, yet each one has its own specific characteristics. Beyond the borders of the archipelago extends the vast ocean of citizen science open to exploration and new knowledge.

The visual identity of the ECS project is based on this metaphor (fig. 1). The logo is composed of 7 coloured circles and a series of dark waves that support them. The circles can be seen as the islands in the archipelago of citizen science. They also represent both the diversity of the citizen science community and the complex structure of the project. While the dark waves are the waves from the vast ocean of citizen science in which ECS navigates and also the possible connections between the islands. The logo has been created in various formats; different variants have also been developed for different parts of the project, one for the ECS Academy, one for the blog, news, media. (fig. 2). In addition to the logo, templates are available for all main types of documents: reports, presentations, and certificates, social media posts (fig. 3).

Figure 1. The main logo of the ECS project, based on the archipelago metaphor and representing the diversity and the complexity of the citizen science community.

Figure 2. Examples of customised logos for the ECS Academy and the ECS blog

Figure 3. Example of use of the social media template for the campaign to the international call for the 28 ECS ambassadors

Our identity and values

The European Citizen Science project is focused on openness and diversity, inclusion and internationality, and aims at empowering the European citizen science community. These efforts will result in a number of key scientific, societal, policy, institutional, technological and economic impacts, defined in work package 8 *Impact Pathways Assessment*, which will strongly contribute to securing Europe's global position as a leader in citizen science throughout the entire research and innovation system, and further strengthen the global citizen science community.

These principles and values are reflected in our vision and mission statements, which must express the concept that we want to become a dynamic, inclusive, and globally connected European citizen science community, that tackles present and future societal challenges and contributes to transformative change. Synthetically these concepts are currently expressed as follows:

ECS Vision

A globally connected, inclusive and strong citizen science community for societal change in Europe

ECS Mission

Creating and sharing data, resources, training and services with communities involved in citizen science, building capacity, and uniting diverse European actors under a common platform

Objectives, audiences and tools

European Citizen Science (ECS) will target various stakeholders to mainstream citizen science, and increase the number of European citizens engaged in citizen science activities. Our approach aims for a wide geographical and disciplinary representation and a range of services and tools will reach out to various audiences to strengthen the dialogue between science and society and for the democratisation of science itself.

Researchers, civil society, policy makers, private sector, formal and non-formal educators, media and media operators will find opportunities to know and appreciate the potential of the citizen science approach. Specific messages and tools will be developed for each audience adapting and developing the general objectives summarised below.

The European Citizen Science project general objectives

Objective 1: Empower the European citizen science community through co-design and co-creation

Objective 2: Strengthen the links and collaboration between existing citizen science initiatives

Objective 3: Increase the participation of citizens from all walks of life in citizen science through an inclusive approach

Objective 4: Build the capacity to conduct excellent research and innovation through citizen science

Objective 5: Raise awareness, support and mainstream citizen science among new actors, new territories and scientific fields

Objective 6: Better align data infrastructures to the needs of citizen science, and improve open science practices employed by citizen science initiatives

Channels of communication

We list here the main channels of communication and refer to the following chapter [Main activities and results](#) for details and outcome.

The [eu-citizen.science platform](#) is the main harbour of the European Citizen Science archipelago. There sailors will find blog posts, interviews, a podcast and other useful content. The platform also hosts all the resources and project outputs and will be enriched by the contributions submitted to the platform by national and regional citizen science initiatives and projects. A dedicated section on the eu-citizen.science platform provides up-to-date information regarding project objectives, progress, results, publications, and reports for different target groups, in a clear and comprehensive way. Information materials are accessible to the wider public. The [eu-citizen.science platform](#) will also be the main access point to the ECS Academy and all the learning and training resources.

Our [social media channels](#) are the most direct link with the community. And it is precisely the community that is the key to the success of the European Citizen Science project: Only through the joint efforts of a strong, cohesive and collaborative community can we altogether achieve our goals.

The [Citizen Science Lighthouse](#), originally planned as a normal project newsletter, has been transformed into a digital magazine published every second month with a brand and an editorial policy. It connects with the ECS collaboration group (WP2) and the content developed and discussed during the monthly meetings. In addition to the usual fresh news from the community, each issue includes an **editorial** written by one member of the consortium which invites reading and highlights the most important themes or connects the magazine issue with notable events, and one or more **long reads focusing on hot topics** in citizen science, mainly those discussed during the ECS collaboration group meetings.

For [internal communication](#), in addition to the usual meetings, we opened a **slack workspace**, including one channel for each work package and additional channels for specific activities and needs.

2. Main activities and results

Social media channels

We have built up our social media communication on the previously existing channels of the EU-Citizen.Science project, and we have been expanding them, creating more engagement, and adding LinkedIn, whose relevance has been growing significantly in the past few years. Social media helps us to create new routes in our citizen science archipelago and reach new islands.

Table 1. ECS social media and its growth 2022-2024

Media	Handle	Followers on August 2022	Followers on 1st July 2024	Increase
Facebook	@EUCitSciProject	1705	2202	+29%
X (formerly Twitter)	@EUCitSciProject	4779	6172	+29%
Instagram	@EU-Citizen.Science	850	1056	+25%
LinkedIn	@eucitsci	-	3280	
TOTAL		7334	12681	+73%

Halfway through the duration of the project, we have therefore already exceeded 10,000 followers, which represent the corresponding KPIs envisaged for social media in the Grant Agreement. Moreover, all consortium organisations have their own social media profiles that have been used to amplify the social media presence of ECS.

ECS inherits an important history on social networks and the community of followers is growing. We will continue to cultivate and nurture it. Yet we are aware of the dramatic changes that have taken place in social media and the related ethical concerns that cannot be ignored. Precisely because social media play a key role for communication and dissemination, it is therefore legitimate and indeed necessary to reflect and keep the conversation open on this topic. Our concerns echo the concerns and discussion of the European Commission, who has opened [formal proceedings](#) to assess whether X may have breached the Digital Services Act (DSA) in areas linked to risk management, content moderation, dark patterns, advertising transparency and data access for researchers. [Updates](#) were published on July 15, with three main preliminary findings:

1. X designs and operates its interface for the “verified accounts” with the “Blue checkmark” in a way that does not correspond to industry practice and **deceives users**. Since anyone can subscribe to obtain such a “verified” status, it negatively affects users' ability to make free and informed decisions about the authenticity of the accounts and the content they interact with.
2. X does not comply with the required **transparency** on advertising.
3. X fails to provide **access to its public data** to researchers.

We remain alert on this issue, continue to follow the discussion at European level and prepare a strategy for a possible exit that is able to mitigate the associated risks.

Communication through visuals

Photos

Photos and video are effective communication tools to convey achievements, results and activities with immediacy. ECS joined the [ECSA Flickr archive](#), opened in 2022, to document events and activities through photos. Today it contains more than 1000 photos, and albums specifically dedicated to ECS, all photos are made available with the creative commons licence (CC BY-NC-SA Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike).

Figure 4. ECS at the ECSA 2024 conference (Vienna, 3-7 April 2024)

Videos

The ECS videos are made publicly available on the [ECSA YouTube channel](#). These videos include the recordings of events organised by ECS. In addition to documenting important workshops and webinars held online, and the **two specific videos presenting ECS** produced in 2023 and 2024. A [short video](#) (30 seconds) introduces the project and can be used during events to showcase our main goals.

A [3-minute video](#), produced with the collaboration of all the partners, from the early stages of designing the concept and the story board up to the filming of the different sections.

Figure 5. A screenshot of the ECS video on the ECSA YouTube channel

The Citizen Science Lighthouse and the eu-citizen.science blog

The Citizen Science Lighthouse

The **Citizen Science Lighthouse** is the bimonthly digital magazine of the ECS project. In addition to the usual news from the community and differently from traditional project newsletters, it has the structure of a proper magazine. Every issue offers readers some long and good reading on topics of interest for the community. The long articles, classified as **Focus**, are written by different authors and enhance the work done by the ECS collaboration group. The topics covered are in general the same addressed in the group's thematic sessions, for example, the importance of training programmes, impact and evaluation tools and strategies, citizen science in education, citizen recruitment, engagement and motivation, citizen science and the law, etc. Each issue is then introduced by an editorial, written by a member of the coordinator organisation.

Synthetically each issue of the Citizen Science Lighthouse is structured as follows:

- Editorial
- 1 or 2 Focus articles
- 10-15 news from the community.

The first issue of the Citizen Science Lighthouse was published in April 2023, after some months of planning that involved the entire consortium: even the title was chosen through a participatory process. It started with 860 readers and now reaches an audience of 1510 readers via mailchimp, showing an increase of 75%.

The complete series is archived [here](#).

The focus articles of each year are collected in **one special issue** published on [zenodo](#) (the open repository for EU-funded research outputs from Horizon Europe, Euratom and earlier Framework Programmes), to further

increase the visibility of our magazine, The special issue 2023 is available [here](#), as part of the [European Citizen Science project community](#).

The eu-citizen.science blog

The eu-citizen.science blog is part of the eu-citizen.science platform, and as such is an open space where the citizen science community can share ideas, projects, interesting reflections, research results, etc. The blog is managed by the European Citizen Science Association within the European Citizen Science project.

The content published is intended to be a useful tool for thought and should provide material of general interest. It must be coherent with the objectives and mission of the eu-citizen.science platform and meet the demands of its target audience, that is everybody interested or working in any capacity in citizen science.

Articles considered suitable for publication:

- articles that are relevant to the general topic of citizen science
- articles presenting research results in citizen science
- articles presenting useful tools for the community
- interviews with relevant protagonists of the community.

Articles connected with commercial activities, or that are not relevant to the general topic of citizen science or are too technical are not considered suitable for the blog.

In the first two years of the ECS project we published **29 blog posts** on a variety of topics, a number that already exceeds the threshold of **20 blog posts** established as **KPIs** by the Grant Agreement. See **Appendix 1** for the complete list of articles published.

Participation to international events and conferences

All partners have been involved in communication and dissemination activities during the first two years of the project. Table 2 summarises the main activities.

Educational trainings: training sessions, summer school, masterclasses, both face-to-face and online, on different aspect of citizen science dedicated to various audiences (educators, researchers, staff of research and public libraries)

Conferences: oral presentations, posters, workshops were held at international conference, covering a wide range of topics and fields

Publications: these include newsletters, blog posts, scientific papers,

Events: round tables, science cafés, open days,

Collaboration and networking: presentation of ECS to joint events with organisations and projects at European level to foster collaboration and make our project more visible

Workshops and webinar: online events to present specific aspects of ECS and mark important milestones.

Table 2. ECS Workshops, Focus sessions, Short trainings, Open formats at ECSA2024 conference

Type of activity	Number
Educational trainings	42
Conferences	20
Publications	46
Events	56
Collaboration and networking	41
Workshops and webinar	11

Among all the international events, we would like to highlight two important ones: the [Ecsite 2024](#) conference (Ljubljana, June 6-8), which brings together over 1,000 experts from science centres and public engagement, and the [Living Knowledge conference](#) (Girona, June 26-28).

At Ecsite 2024, ECS presented the project in a showcase session and participated in a panel dedicated to training in participatory science. At the Living Knowledge conference, the prototype of the first discussion game [Playdecide](#) dedicated to citizen science was presented. Both conferences were an opportunity to network and increase the visibility of ECS and the potential of citizen science in communities where it is still marginal.

The ECSA 2024 conference

The ECSA conferences are one of the most important events for the citizen science community. This year it was held in Vienna from 3 to 6 April, hosted by BOKU University, Österreich Forscht (the Austrian citizen science network) and the Naturhistorische Museum Wien.

[ECSA2024 conference](#) focused on the motto 'Change', to address the dramatic and rapid changes we are experiencing through the citizen science approach. The conference was attended by almost 500 people from almost all European countries and representatives from Africa, Asia, South and North America.

Figure 6. The ECSA2024 poster

The ECS project was present with various coordinated initiatives that allowed great visibility and impact. Table 3 shows the list of all the sessions in which ECS was the protagonist.

Table 3. ECS Workshops, Focus sessions, Short trainings, Open formats at the ECSA2024 conference

When	Session	Title	Partners
Wednesday 3 April	Workshop	Co-designing the future of European citizen science: a participatory workshop for eu-citizen.science	ECSA, Ibercivis, Stickydot, UP
Wednesday 3 April	Focus	Rethinking impact assessment of citizen science	ZSI
Wednesday 3 April	Training	Boosting inclusion in citizen science research processes: why diversity matters	SfC
Wednesday 3 April	Workshop	Increasing the diversity and visibility of the citizen science community's contributions to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	MfN
Wednesday 3 April	Poster	Collective intelligence for adapting to climate change: monitoring the Arctic by expedition cruises	Nordeco
Wednesday 3 April	Poster	Community-based monitoring in the Arctic	Nordeco
Wednesday 3 April	Poster	Best practices in citizen science infrastructures	CSIC
Thursday 4 April	Workshop	Co-designing guidelines for policy-makers for mainstreaming and upscaling citizen science across the European Research Area	SfC
Thursday 4 April	Poster	Expanding and engaging the citizen science community in Europe	ECSA
Friday 5 April	Workshop	European Citizen Science Academy (ECS Academy) - what is in it for you? A call to collaboration	UP, ECSA, MCAA
Saturday 6 April	Citizen Science Day	Your desirable futures	All partners, and Wien KinderBüro

On April 25 the sixth issue of the ECS digital magazine the **Citizen Science Lighthouse** was dedicated to highlight the best moments of our participation in the ECSA2024 conference. The main contributions were also published on the eu-citizen.science blog (table 4).

Table 4. Blog posts on the ECS participation to the ECSA2024 conference

Author	Title	Link
Dorte Riemenschneider	ECSA2024 conference in Vienna: a memorable event	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2024/04/24/ecsa2024-conference-in-vienna-a-memorable-event/
Stefanie Schuerz, Teresa Schäfer, Barbara Kieslinger	Rethinking impact assessment of citizen science	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2024/04/24/rethinking-impact-assessment-in-citizen-science/
Simona Cerrato	Our desirable futures	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2024/04/24/our-desirable-futures/

Horizon Results Booster

Horizon Results Booster (**HRB**) is an initiative of the European Commission which aims to bring a continual stream of innovation to the market and maximise the impact of public funded research within the EU. It supports projects eager to go beyond their Dissemination and Exploitation (D&E) obligations – steering research towards strong societal impact and concretising the value of Research and Innovation (R&I) activity for societal challenges. To achieve this, HRB offers free consulting services to closed or ongoing research projects funded by FP7, Horizon 2020, or Horizon Europe programmes.

ECS joined the programme in November 2023, together with the projects REINFORCING and PATTERN. The first phase of the Horizon Results Booster (Service 1 Module A), to identify and create the portfolio of R&I project results, was completed on February 27, 2024, with the collaboration of the ECS relevant partners. In May 2024, the second phase started (Module B) which aims at helping projects to design and execute a portfolio of joint dissemination activities. It will end in September 2024. The last phase (Module C) will be focused on improving the existing exploitation strategy.

3. Global collaborations

As part of the WP6, the T6.3 *Global citizen science network* aims to build connections and strengthen the citizen science global community to help mainstream citizen science, and to position Europe as a leader in citizen science throughout the entire research and innovation system.

This has been done through three main ways:

- a. The network of the 28 ECS citizen science ambassadors
- b. The participation in the World Environment Situation Room (WESR) organised by the Citizen Science Global Partnership ([CSGP](#))
- c. The collaboration with SciStarter for the CitSci months 2022, 2023 and 2024.

We continue in close contact with the CSGT board to build more synergies and find new ways to support one another.

The network of the 28 ECS citizen science ambassadors

The campaigns to recruit the 28 ECS citizen science ambassadors were held in May 2023 and September-October 2023 (see Figure 7). The ambassadors' task is to support the activities in the project, raise awareness about citizen science and spread and strengthen citizen science in Europe.

The complete list of the 28 ambassadors is available on the corresponding [page](#) on the eu-citizen.science platform.

Figure 7. Example of social media post for the campaign to recruit the ECS ambassadors

Each ambassador represents the link between the European level and the local and national levels, and a new spot on our navigation chart in the vast ocean of citizen science. In their capacity they are also building

connections with the national networks and associations – where they exist – or help to create them from scratch.

Table 5. The ECS citizen science ambassadors and their connections with the national associations and networks

Country	Ambassadors	Association/Network	Remarks
Austria	Didone Frigerio	Österreich Forscht	The Austrian network was partner of the ECSA2024 conference
Belgium	Annelies Duerinckx	Scivil	ECS is included in the Citizen Science Inspiration and Networking Day that will take place on 12 September
Bulgaria	Stefaniya Kamenova		
Croatia	Tea Vukušić Rukavina		
Cyprus	Natasha Andronikou	Citizens in power	
Czech Republic	Michael Lažan	Citizen Science CZ	
Denmark	Gitte Kragh	Citizen science Netværket and the Citizen Science Knowledge Centre	Active in the ECS from the beginning and in the ECSA working group activities.
Estonia	Veljo Runnel	Loodusveeb	
Finland	Alexandra Middleton	FACTZ	
France	Angelee Pavanee Annasawmy		
Germany	Jasmin Pfeifer	Mit:Forschen	
Greece	Vasiliki (Vassia) Fragkaki		
Hungary	Marietta Le		
Ireland	Oscar Diaz	Citizen Science Ireland	On July 4th Oscar Diaz and the Trinity College organise a face-to-face event to establish a

			citizen science network in Ireland
Italy	Gaia Agnello	Citizen Science Italia	ECS, Gaia Agnello and the president of the association Andrea Sforzi organised a community event within the first conference of the association (23-26 November 2023)
Latvia	Sanita Reinsone		
Lithuania	Monika Mačiulienė	Piliėciu Mokslas	
Luxembourg	Federica Moretti	Nexus Citizen Science Luxembourg	
Malta	Simone Cutajar		
Netherlands	Diana Wildschut	Citizen Science Netherlands	
Poland	Bogna Gawrońska-Nowak		
Portugal	Rita Rocha		
Romania	Lucrina Stefanescu		
Slovakia	Zuzana Stožická		
Slovenia	Zarja Muršič	Meza občanske znanosti v Sloveniji	
Spain	Meritxell Abril		
Sweden	Lotta Waesterberg Tomasson	Vetenskap & Allmänhet	It is an independent Swedish non-profit membership organisation that works to promote dialogue and openness between researchers and the public and includes citizen science.
United Kingdom	Adrian Cooper		

Through the network of the ECS citizen science ambassadors ECS created links with five national citizen science associations or networks. These ties will be further strengthened in the next two years, while other connections are underway.

The participation in the WESR organised with the CSGP

ECS is represented in the Citizen Science Global Partnership ([CSGP](#)), which is a network of the world's leading regional and national citizen science associations that a) seeks to promote and advance citizen science for a sustainable world, b) generates new citizen science initiatives at a local and global scale and c) supports North-South collaborations. It includes [ECSA](#) (the European Citizen Science Association), the [Australian Citizen Science Association](#), CitSci Africa Association, [CitizenScience.Asia](#), [RICAP](#) (Red Iberoamericana de Ciencia Participativa), [AASP](#) (the USA Association for Advancing Participatory Sciences).

This activity aims to further explore the ocean of citizen science, reaching new islands through new routes. During the year 2023-2024, ECS has participated in the World Environment Situation Room (WESR) working group of the [UNEP](#) (United Nation Environment Programme) to set up the Citizen Science Portal. This first stage involved: 1. updating the current structure to more effectively highlight the best available citizen science data and metadata, 2. designing the new structure based on eight sections, 3. defining the criteria that will guide regional citizen associations in selecting projects for inclusion from each region.

The collaboration with SciStarter for the CitSci months 2023, 2024

The **Citizen Science Month** is an initiative of [SciStarter](#), a network based in the USA that helps bring together people and offers thousands of opportunities to engage in real-world research questions in collaboration with researchers, communities, organisations, and companies. SciStarter also offers resources, products, and services that enable people to pursue and enjoy these activities while learning and accelerating important research.

ECS and ECSA were active part of the CitSci months 2023 and 2024, contributing to the campaign [One Million Act Of Science](#), mainly through social media. In July 2024, we started to plan the CitSci Month 2025 within a frame of a more organic and strategic collaboration with SciStarter, with the aim to make it more relevant also at a European level.

4. Conclusions and next steps

The first two years have been highly productive and positive in terms of communication and dissemination. The archipelago metaphor has helped to make our brand recognizable, and the community has grown. All partners have contributed to the collective effort of making the project visible and increasing its impact.

Most of the KPIs established in the grant agreement have already been achieved (Table 6), and this is certainly a positive sign.

We are particularly satisfied with the ECS products, in particular the Citizen Science Lighthouse magazine produced in collaboration with the ECS collaboration group and the two videos, which are professional and engaging, and the presence at many international events.

In the next two years, we will be committed to further developing all communication and dissemination activities, in particular by launching a series of video blogs in collaboration with the network of 28 ECS citizen science ambassadors and with the contribution of all partners who wish to do so, and the podcast series. The ECSA Communication Office will continue to support all partners in their activities, contributing to creating a greater sense of belonging and commitment to the project.

The communication activities were well designed in the Grant Agreement and were carried out according to the strategic communication and dissemination plan prepared in November 2022. This date marks the outset of the actions that have been continued throughout the first two years. We were able to call attention of multiple audiences about citizen science and its potential, by valuing the transnational cooperation in our consortium (i.e. how working together has allowed us to achieve more than otherwise possible) and the scientific excellence of the partners. We were able to reach out to most of the target audiences identified in the D6.1 *Communication and dissemination Plan*: researchers, citizen science practitioners, platform users and developers, policy makers, libraries, educators, R&I institutions. A particular effort has been put in using inclusive communication, in the language, the choice of topics and images, avoiding stereotypes and biases.

Yet more efforts must be put to reach out to other audiences, such as industries and the media, who have been targeted only in rare cases, and in a non-systematic way. We continue to work towards *Boosting inclusion and diversity for mainstreaming citizen science* as part of WP5, who despite a slow couple of months due to staff exchange is now on full steam enabling. This will enable us to work more robustly towards including different groups of audiences, both by geographical distribution and by belonging to communities or social groups that for various reasons are excluded from authentic participation in science and citizen science.

Table 6. KPIs corresponding to communications and dissemination activities

Media	KPIs foreseen in th GA	Actual status	Difference
Social media	10.000 followers	12.681	+2681
Blog posts	20 posts	29	+9

Citizen Science Lighthouse	1000 subscribers	1510	+510
Videos	600 views	132 on YouTube + >250 during events = >350	- 250
Podcast	500 listeners	Not started	-
National citizen science associations and networks involved	6	5 national associations + the CSGP + SciStarted = 7	+ 1

Appendix 1. Articles published on the eu-citizen.science blog (July 2022-July 2024)

Authors	Title	Date of publication	Link
Juliette Chalant	Citizen science and the libraries: the stories of the Valmiera Library, Latvia	10.07.2014	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2024/07/10/citizen-science-and-the-libraries-the-stories-of-the-valmiera-library-latvia/
Simona Cerrato	Michael Køie Poulsen, A Champion for Biodiversity and Sustainable Development, passed away	27.06.2024	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2024/06/27/michael-koie-poulsen-a-champion-for-biodiversity-and-sustainable-development-passed-away/
Andrea Sforzi	Italy: the NBFC Working Table on Citizen Science was born	17.06.2024	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2024/06/17/italy-the-nbfc-working-table-on-citizen-science-was-born/
Simona Cerrato	Training is key!	17.06.2024	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2024/06/17/training-is-key/
Stefanie Schuerz	Rethinking impact assessment in citizen science	24.04.2024	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2024/04/24/rethinking-impact-assessment-in-citizen-science/
Simona Cerrato	Our desirable futures	24.04.2024	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2024/04/24/our-desirable-futures/
Dorte Riemenschneider	ECSA2024 conference in Vienna: a memorable event	24.04.2024	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2024/04/24/ecsa2024-conference-in-vienna-a-memorable-event/
Sonia Liñán	ECS Best Practices report for collaborative data infrastructures	08.02.2024	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2024/02/08/ecs-best-practices-report-collaborative-data-infrastructures/

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Cathrine M. S. Winther	Citizen social science in educational settings	31.01.2024	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2024/01/31/citizen-social-science-educational-settings/
Yaela Golumbic	Education and training at the Israel Center for Citizen Science	31.01.2024	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2024/01/31/education-and-training-israel-center-citizen-science/
Floor Keersmaekers	Urban engaged university	31.01.2024	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2024/01/31/urban-engaged-university/
Simona Cerrato	Behind the Scenes of the First National Conference of Citizen Science Italia	23.01.2024	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2024/01/23/behind-scenes-first-national-conference-citizen-science-italia/
Simona Cerrto	Dietro le quinte del primo Convegno nazionale di Citizen Science Italia	23.01.2024	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2024/01/23/dietro-le-quinte-del-primo-convegno-nazionale-di-citizen-science-italia/
Meritxell Martell	European Radon Day marked with citizen science event	05.12.2023	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2023/12/05/european-radon-day-marked-citizen-science-event/
Antonio Filograna, Meritxell Martell and Florence Gignac	Citizen engagement, motivation and recruitment	01.12.2023	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2023/12/01/citizen-engagement-motivation-and-recruitment/
Claudia Fabó Cartas	A wrap-up of 2023 in the ECS project	01.12.2023	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2023/12/01/wrap-2023-ecs-project/
Katerina Zourou, Stefania Oikonomou	Citizen science in conflict zones for community empowerment	27.11.2023	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2023/11/27/citizen-science-conflict-zones-community-empowerm

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Annelies Duerinckx	Legal challenges for citizen science initiatives: Stories from the field	02.10.2023	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2023/10/02/focus-legal-challenges-citizen-science-initiatives-stories-field/
Anna Berti Suman	Citizen science and the law: potential applications	02.10.2023	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2023/10/02/focus-citizen_science_and_the_law/
Anna Sanchez Vidal	Sharing results with citizens	02.10.2023	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2023/07/25/focus-sharing-results-citizens/
Simona Cerrato	Editorial: Our house is on fire	25.07.2023	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2023/07/25/editorial-our-house-fire/
Stefanie Schuerz	Citizen science for social transformation: Measuring the impact of citizen science initiatives	01.06.2023	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2023/06/01/citizen-science-social-transformation-measuring-impact-citizen-science-initiatives/
Claudia Fabó Cartas	Welcome to the Citizen Science Lighthouse	01.06.2023	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2023/06/01/welcome-citizen-science-lighthouse/
Florence Gignac	Let's navigate together through the sea of citizen science in Europe!	01.06.2023	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2023/06/01/lets-navigate-together-through-the-sea-of-citizen-science/
Simona Cerrato	Citizen science and machine learning: a promising partnership	15.03.2023	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2023/03/15/citizen-science-and-machine-learning-promising-partnership/
Andrea Troncoso	Kick 2023 off the right way! A fantastic opportunity for Citizen	10.01.2023	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2023/01/10/fanta

	Science projects who go that extra step!		stic-opportunity-citizen-science-projects/
Simona Cerrato	What teens have to say about their health	09.01.2023	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2023/01/09/what-teens-have-say-about-their-health/
Simona Cerrato	European Citizen Science: the communication and dissemination plan in a nutshell	27.12.2022	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2022/12/27/ecs-communication-and-dissemination-plan/
Andrea Troncoso	Save the date! 2023 starts with an Open Call for citizen science initiatives!	20.12.2022	https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2022/12/20/open-call-citizen-science-initiatives/